

Predicting wetness perception on car seats

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Introduction

Sweat production during summertime inside vehicle cabins may lead to an accumulation of heat and moisture at the seat-person interface [1] increasing microclimate vapour pressure ($p_{mic,cl}$) and skin wettedness (w_{sk}) [2] and consecutively causing local thermal discomfort [3]. Though there is an incremental use of thermal manikins and models for evaluating vehicle thermal comfort [4], the underlying comfort models focus on the convective and radiative heat transfer [5, 6] disregarding evaporation associated with wetness perception (WP) [7]. Therefore, this study aimed at providing a model predicting WP by physical ($p_{mic,cl}$) and physiological (w_{sk}) quantities serving as benchmarks in manikin and model simulations.

Methods

Sitting on a car seat, 56 females and 56 males clothed with jeans and T-shirt (0.6 clo) were exposed for 2 h in a climatic chamber to 25 °C air temperature, 60 °C mean radiant temperature, 1.58 kPa water vapour pressure and 0.5 m/s air velocity. Using a Pt100 sensor combined with a capacitance hygrometer (Vaisala HMP 233) we continuously recorded temperature and relative humidity of the seat-clothing microclimate at the cushion and the backrest, from which we calculated microclimate vapour pressure. For a sub-sample of 23 females and 20 males, we also measured microclimate humidity at the skin-clothing layer, which we used together with corresponding skin temperature measurements (thermistor YSI 427) to calculate w_{sk} at seat cushion and backrest, respectively. We registered WP every 5 min in the first hour and every 10 min in the second hour of exposure applying a 5-point scale (1='dry', 2='slightly moist', 3='moist', 4='wet', 5='very wet'), which we dichotomized applying a cut-off scale value greater than two for classifying a vote as a definite WP.

Applying logistic regression analyses [8], we first compared the predictive capabilities of w_{sk} and $p_{mic,cl}$ on WP by calculating the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for the subsample (n=43). We then used the whole data set (n=112) to develop a model predicting WP by $p_{mic,cl}$ and other factors, e.g. exposure time. We finally validated the model by comparing the predicted percentage with WP to observations in an earlier study comprising 214 heat exposures [9].

Figure 1. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves with areas in parentheses comparing the capabilities of skin wettedness (w_{sk}) and vapour pressure at the clothing-seat-interface ($p_{mic,cl}$) to predict WP at the car seat's cushion (left panel) and backrest (right panel) regions, respectively.

Figure 2. (a) Predictions of WP at the backrest by vapour pressure at the clothing-seat-interface ($p_{mic,cl}$) and exposure time; and (b) comparison to percentages observed for males and females at the cushion and backrest in independent test trials with at least 50 observations for each data point [9].

Results and discussion

The ROC analyses (Fig. 1) revealed that $p_{mic,cl}$ was at least as good a predictor of WP as w_{sk} for both the seat cushion and backrest. This may partly reflect the lack of specific humidity sensors in the human skin so that WP is mediated by sensing evaporative cooling or stickiness [7], both related to vapour pressure. The predictive model for WP thus included $p_{mic,cl}$, but also exposure time as additional predictor for both the backrest (Fig. 2a) and the cushion (not shown), indicating a general increase of discomfort with exposure time. The predictions were highly correlated to independent observations (Fig. 2b) with a slight underestimation bias not exceeding 10%.

Conclusions

The results suggest that vapour pressure at the clothing-seat interface may validly predict wetness perception on car seats under heat stress, thus allowing for conveniently coupling human thermal comfort models with physical data from manikin measurements or from model simulations.

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